

bog : Instrumental Aliens

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Biographical information

Masato Takahashi : Sound + Device creator. He was born in 1984. He has studied computer music at Graduate School of Media and Governance, Keio University. He has researched musical expression and produced variety of musical instruments.

Hiroya Tanaka : Media Architect / Associate Professor at Keio University. Dr, Eng. He was born in 1975. His interests are architectural design, information design and device developments. Tanaka laboratory has kicked off in 2004. The laboratory covers wide ranges of contemporary and interdisciplinary designs using digital technologies.

Description of Piece

bogs is new aliens -the hybridization between instruments and creatures-.

Typically, Japanese take good care of their belongings as if they are all alive. In the case of musical instrument players, they tend to love their instruments like their pets. Taking this point as a hint, we aim to inject "spirits" into musical instruments

bogs have two types of sensors inside. The air pressure sensor captures a change of internal air pressure, and the two-axis acceleration sensor monitors delicate hand movements of a user. Interacting with each other at the stage of sound generation, captured data carried by the sensors expand the *bogs*' expression.

The computers perform as sound generators based on data transmitted by *bogs*. *bogs* produce not clear sounds, but virtual voices. An audio processing system, using formant synthesis for voice generation, works with Max/MSP. Sensor data fill in variables of formant synthesis program on this system, and bring about a complicated and continuous change of "voices".

We are eager to spread *bogs* into many places and enlarge their habitation areas all over the world.

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